

Anonymous Test	
Category	Participant Quotes
Impaired Readability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1: "I believe it would impact (negatively) [...] It should be something that explains what's being tested in fact." • P2: "This would be even worse than the first case [...] you force the need to read the code body." • P3: "When a test isn't clear in its description [...]. We can't define the context without having to read the entire code." • P6: "I see this as practically the same, or perhaps even worse than the last one [...] it's so vague, they might think it's about one thing when, in reality, it's about something else." • P8: "I also don't see any positive aspects. Depending on the context, it may be useful to separate blocks, and functions should throw errors, but a description of the type of error that will be thrown is necessary. However, I can't see anything positive with these two words (in the test description)." • P9: "What I see is that the lack of a clear description causes the developer... In repetitive tests[...] they might end up testing something more than once due to the lack of clarity." • P10: "I've encountered situations like this before [...] I make sure to correct it to make it as clear as possible...I always try to make it as descriptive as possible [...]" • P12: "I think it falls into the same problem of not having any description. It's almost as if the test is missing a description anyway. If you don't understand what a test is doing, someone might come later and remove it or change it without realizing its purpose."
Useless or Misleading Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1: "I believe it would impact (negatively) [...] It should be something that explains what's being tested in fact." • P6: "I see this as practically the same, or perhaps even worse than the last one [...] it's so vague, they might think it's about one thing when, in reality, it's about something else." • P8: "I also don't see any positive aspects. Depending on the context, it may be useful to separate blocks, and functions should throw errors, but a description of the type of error that will be thrown is necessary. However, I can't see anything positive with these two words (in the test description)."
Maintenance Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P9: "What I see is that the lack of a clear description leads the developer... In repetitive tests, due to the lack of clarity, they might end up testing something more than once unintentionally." • P6: "I think it falls into the same problem of not having any description at all. It's almost as if the test is missing a description anyway. If you don't understand what a test is doing, someone might come later and remove or change it without realizing its purpose."

Comments Only Test	
Category	Participant Quotes
Dead Code and Visual Pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P4: "These comments here are useless. Checking if the ID is 1 doesn't even make sense to comment." • P5: "It's basically dead code, probably not helping at all [...] it just causes more problems than it's worth because it's not doing anything." • P6: "Commented code is rarely uncommented." • P8: "I agree this can make code visibility difficult." • P10: "Tools like SonarQube will flag commented code [...] sometimes you comment something and completely forget about it." • P13: "A commented test might mean that the person was working on a feature and left it there for convenience."
Acceptable Cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P4: "Maybe the build broke, or it was a critical bug update, and someone had to comment out the test to pass the build." • P4: "If there was a comment explaining why, while it would still be bad, at least we would know why it was commented out." • P8: "The only useful case would be if it was a functionality you had in the project that wasn't working, or if you needed to revert." • P10: "I've done this before, but only while still developing the feature. While it's still in progress [...] it's okay."
Versioning misuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P6: "We have code versioning tools available; if you maintain good commit standards per PR, you can see and go back."

Overcommented Test	
Category	Participant Quotes
Redundancy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P3: "Using comments as documentation [...] calling a function and checking something is unnecessary for test code" • P4: "Makes tests harder to read [...] comments lose meaning when outdated" • P5: "They repeat what the next line does [...] just redundancy that should be removed" • P8: "Code should be self-explanatory with good naming" • P12: "Too many comments look lazy [...] visual clutter"
Poorly Written Code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1: "Needing many comments means your code isn't good" • P2: "Comments often compensate for poorly written code" • P3: "People use comments to document bad code" • P12: "Clean Code principles favor clarity without comments"
Maintenance Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P4: "Outdated comments mislead developers"
Acceptable Cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P5: "Only for non-obvious complex logic" • P8: "Potentially valid for educational purposes" • P10: "Only worthwhile for very specific cases" • P13: "Only for very specific situations"

Sensitivity Equality	
Category	Participant Quotes
Unjustified Complexity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1: "I think the problem lies in using unnecessary additional methods, right? It ends up impacting performance by consuming resources unnecessarily." • P2: "I'd need to think of an example where it would make sense to use it [...] Is there any reason to need toString in this case?" • P3: "There's no need to use it. I work with data structures and only use toString when I'm really forced to convert some type of data, [...] So I think maybe, in this case—like in the test example—it's unnecessary. There's no need to use it." • P4: "I haven't seen any scenario where it would be necessary to use toString. And I think it gets in the way. It makes the test more verbose." • P5: "I agree, and I think that especially with JavaScript, not TypeScript, if for some reason getUser returns... Well, that would make the test fail since there would be no match, but the error wouldn't be related to the functionality—it would be due to how the test was written..." • P6: "I think there might be cases where could be used, but I can't think of any right now, and it affects both readability—since it's an extra method to read—and the effectiveness of the test..." • P12: "I think that, in this case, testing primitive types is not a good idea. If you have an integer, you can easily compare it with another integer, especially because assignment works by value in these cases..."
Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P5: "What ends up harming the reliability of the test is that the error occurs, but not for the right reasons or in the correct way, and that can sometimes cause confusion." • P6: "For example, if getUser returns an age as a number and, for some reason, your code breaks and returns a string instead, it won't catch that error."
Performance and Readability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1: "I think the problem lies in using unnecessary additional methods, right? It ends up impacting performance by using resources unnecessarily." • P6: "This affects readability as well, since it's an extra method to read."
Acceptable Cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P10: "I've never encountered this situation either, but I can imagine a scenario where it could be used. For example, in a database, you store a value as an integer, but on the front end, you need to pass it as a string. In that case, you'd convert from integer to string..." • P12: "And for cases where you want to compare objects. Objects are by reference in memory. When you want to compare whether two objects are equal, testing tools like Vitest already have methods for that. You can use JSON.stringify() to compare the values as strings. If something goes wrong with <code>!texttt(stringify)</code>, you'll probably have to debug it with Vitest as well."

General Fixture	
Category	Participant Quotes
Lack of Independence Between Tests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P2: "One of the test blocks could alter the existing values... this would break the other tests that haven't run yet." • P4: "If another test modifies some mocked data, it will end up impacting another one."
Unnecessary Resource Allocation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P3: "The problem with tests that rely on fixtures is that, if there's an issue with a fixture, right, all test cases linked to it will fail, they'll break. So, this dependency issue, I think, can be a risk..." • P4: "There's also a point in this example where there's a mock for the guest, but it's not used in the tests... it's unused code, and it serves no purpose [...] Unnecessary code always causes problems [...]" • P5: "I agree with P6, especially in rare exceptions. I think there are really few exceptions where mocked data makes sense. Usually, I think of situations where you have a controller that needs to do something, and you want to know if that controller's functionality is working..." • P6: "I'm really against testing with mocked data because, as you can see, it's not testing anything. [...] in reality, it's not testing anything, and that's a bit dangerous because if you change something in your code [...]"
Tight Coupling and Risk of False Positives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P3: "The problem with tests that depend on fixtures is that if there's an issue with a fixture, right, all test cases linked to it will fail, they'll break. So, this dependency issue, I think, can be a risk. If you have a fixture and many test cases depend on it to pass, then any change or issue with that fixture or mocked data will cause all those tests to break..." • P4: "There is also a point in this example where there is a mock for the guest, but it is not used in the tests... it's unused code, and it serves no purpose; in any case, it gets in the way..." • P6: "I'm really against testing with mocked data because, as you can see, you're not actually testing anything. You could change anything in your database, and the test would still pass—unless you change the user class, admin, or guest..." • P5: "I agree with P6, especially in rare exceptions. I think there are very few cases where mocked data actually makes sense. [...] Personally, I don't like mocks either. I feel like I'm not really testing anything, because I'm defining what's going to come in, so there's no unpredictability—everything is already within what I expect."
Justified Use of Mocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P9: "Well, in unit tests, from my point of view, it is highly recommended to use mocks. Because when you are testing a unit of code, you are testing the smallest functionality within your code..." • P10: "I see this test being useful only if you are testing the entity itself..." • P11: "If it's just to test the constructor, for example, and it's not spread throughout the code, I don't see any problem in using the describe." • P12: "I don't think it's a problem. You have a hook or dedicated function in Vitex that allows you to create a new mock before each test. This prevents you from using the same mock instance between tests. It avoids interference between tests. So, I don't think it affects the independence of the test." • P13: "I don't see a risk, since you are defining it within a specific block. You're not spreading it around randomly. If the describe block is entirely about that, then it's fine. If not, you can always reorganize."

Test Without Description	
Category	Participant Quotes
Debugging Difficulty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1: “If we run the test and it fails [...] Without a description, debugging the code becomes difficult.” • P2: “You have to read the entire body to understand what is happening.” • P6: “I don’t see any positive aspect; this would only increase the work of checking the function to understand what is being tested.” • P12: “Imagine if there were multiple lines of code—you would have to stop working to check why it is failing or passing.”
Loss of Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P2: “A test should also serve as documentation [...] it loses that value.” • P13: “I agree that a test serves as a form of documentation. And if you don’t describe what you’re testing, you’re losing one of its functionalities.
Misinterpretation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P10: “Besides requiring more time to understand what the code is doing, there is also the risk of misinterpreting its intent.”

Transcribing Test	
Category	Participant Quotes
Principle Violations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1: "In this case, I don't see keeping logs as a good practice, right? During development, when you need to debug using logs, it's sometimes necessary, but when you're going to, say, make a commit or deploy to production or staging, I don't think it's a good practice to keep logs in your code." • P2: "When you have a test suite, a large test file, let's say, and each one has two or three logs, it starts adding up and becomes a lot of code clutter. So, it's a practice we try to avoid." • P8: "I'm not sure if I should add this, but I think when you use console.log this way—which I also don't consider ideal—it might indicate issues in the code during testing." • P9: "But if we're using logs in unit tests, we're violating one of the core principles of unit testing, which is interacting with the external environment by redirecting strings to the user's console output." • P12: "I think it adds an extra function call, which has an impact. You end up testing something that isn't really relevant—basically, you're testing the log itself. This introduces another function call during execution, which, even if minimal, can affect runtime performance."
Test Structure Problem (complexity or excessive size)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P4: "If the log is trying to describe something in the test, that should be handled by the test's own description. If you need it, perhaps the test is too large and you should split it." • P12: "If you need a console.log to understand an error message that should have been split or clarified elsewhere, that's a problem."
Code Pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P4: "If the log is trying to describe something in the test, that should be handled by the test's own description. If you need it, perhaps the test is too large and you should split it." • P12: "If you need a console.log to understand an error message that should have been split or clarified elsewhere, that's a problem."
Acceptable temporary use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P5: "I think it's fine to use console.log when you're testing and building something, especially when you're modifying something in the test. [...] It's more useful when you're updating something in the test or when you deliberately make a test fail first and then fix it. [...]. It's just more useful when you're actively testing and creating the test." • P6: "I think logs in tests can have some usefulness'd [...] prefer it to be done through variable names or function calls instead of logs. But if there's a log with some kind of information, I personally don't mind. I'm not a fan of it, but it doesn't bother me."
Acceptable in backend	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P13: "I have the opposite opinion. I worked at a place where backend logs were really necessary. They helped debug issues in production by showing where something went wrong. [...]" • P10: "I'm a backend developer, and from what I see, logs are widely used in backend code [...] within test code, they're quite rare, you know? [...] And this impacts the readability of test code I'm speaking specifically about test code here [...] we don't need those logs in the console within test files."